

Phytochemical Investigation and Elemental Analysis of Leaves of *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham. and Its Antioxidant Activity

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Abstract

The selected plant, *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham. belongs to the family Lythraceae. Vernacular name of this plant is Pinlel-zeethee in Myanmar, Ponlel-zathee in Rakhine. *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham. was collected from Sittway Township, Rakhine State. According to the traditional systems of medicines, such as Ayurveda and Unani, *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham. possesses antioxidant activity. Local people use this plant as vegetable. Thus *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham. emphasized in studying for its phytochemical constituents, element contents and antioxidant activity. In phytochemical analysis, the result showed that alkaloids, glycosides, phenolic compounds, flavonoids, steroids, terpenoids, tannins, saponins, α amino acids, proteins, reducing sugars, starch and carbohydrate were observed. Elemental analysis of *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham. were also detected by using Energy Dispersive X-ray Fluorescence (EDXRF) spectrometry to know the concentration of principle elements and trace elements that may be present in plants. Chlorine, Potassium, Calcium, Sulphur, Iron, Manganese, Bromine, Zinc, Copper, and Rubidium were detected. The toxic elements were also analyzed by Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (AAS). Arsenic, Cadmium and Lead were observed. Antioxidant activity of leaves is also detected by DPPH essay method. The result indicated that leaves of *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham. has the radical scavenging (antioxidant) activity.

Key words: *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham., phytochemical constituents, elemental analysis, antioxidant activity

Introduction

The selected mangrove plant, *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham. is a fast-growing evergreen tree with a columnar crown; it can grow up to 15 meters in height. The tree produces pneumatophores up to 1.5 metres in length. *Sonneratia* is a genus of plants in the family Lythraceae. Formerly the *Sonneratia* were placed in a family called Sonneratiaceae which included both the *Sonneratia* and the *Duabanga*, but these two are now placed in their own monotypic subfamilies of the family Lythraceae. (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sonneratia>)

There are increasing threats to mangrove swamps in general, mainly from human activities. Consequently, the tree has been classified as 'Least Concern' in the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. Mangroves are a collection of plants growing in saline coastal habitats and are rich sources of secondary metabolites. Which possess interesting bioactive properties. In the traditional systems of medicines, such as Ayurveda and Unani, *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham. possesses antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-bacterial, anti-fungal, anthelmintic, cytotoxic/anticancer, anti-diarrheal, analgesic, anti-diabetic, and anti-hyperlipidemic activities.

Sonneratia apetala Buch. Ham, also known as mangrove apple plant. It is grown as a tree or shrub along seaward fringes and intertidal areas. This plant has been traditionally used to treat hepatitis. The leaf part of the plant is widely used for dysentery, sprain and bruises, in treatment of eye troubles (such as cataract) and open sores in children ears and also in heart troubles. Stem is used for paper pulp, matches, and as poles, leaves as fodder. Its fruits are used as vegetable due to its sour taste and which is marketed. However, very little is known about the specific chemical constituents present in this plant. Thus, the present study aims to determine phytochemical constituents, elements contents and antioxidant activity of the selected plant.

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Materials and Methods

Preliminary Phytochemical Investigation

Powdered leaves of *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham. were tested for their chemical constituents such as reducing sugar, alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids and steroids, cyanogenetic glycosides, saponins, carbohydrates, tannins, starch, phenolic compounds and amino acids etc. The experimental procedure was prepared by the methods mention in Central Council for Research in Marini- Bettolo G.B *et al*, 1981; Unani Medicine, 1987; WHO (1998) and Trease and Evans, 2002.

Elemental Study

Element contents were analyzed by using Energy Dispersive X-ray Florescence (EDXRF) spectrometer. Determination of toxic elements was carried out by using Atomic Absorption spectrometer (AAS) at Universities' Research Center (URC), Yangon University.

Screening of Antioxidant Activity

Antioxidant activity was measured by DPPH (2-2 Diphenyl-1-Picrylhydrazyl) assay method at the department of small scale industries, North Okkalpa, Yangon.

The following are used in DPPH free radical scavenging assay methods

- Powder samples
- DPPH (2-2 Diphenyl-1-Picrylhydrazyl)
- Ascorbic acids
- Ethanol
- Distilled Water
- Spectrophotometer

Results

Figure 1. Habit

Figure 2. Leaves

Figure 3. Inflorescence

Figure 4. Flower

Figure 5. Fruits

Phytochemical investigation of leaves of *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham.

For preliminary phytochemical screening, powders were subjected to different qualitative chemical tests to determine the presence or absence of various phytochemical constituents. Alkaloids, glycosides, phenolic compounds, flavonoids, steroid and terpenoids, tannins, saponin, α -Amino acids, proteins, reducing sugar, starch and carbohydrates were observed. The experimental results were shown on the following table.

Table 1. Phytochemical Tests of the leaves of *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham.

No	Test	Extracts	Test reagent	Observation	Remark
1.	Alkaloids		1% HCl + Mayer's reagent 1% HCl + Wanger's reagent 1% HCl + Hager's reagent	White ppt. Reddish brown ppt. Yellow ppt.	+ + +
2.	Glycosides	MeOH	1 ml H ₂ O + NaOH	Yellow-Green	+
3.	Phenolic compound	MeOH	2 ml H ₂ O + 10% FeCl ₃	Blackish green	+
4.	Flavonoids	MeOH	Mg coil + HCL (dil.)	Pink colour	+
5.	Steroid/ Terpenoid	MeOH	CHCl ₃ + H ₂ SO ₄ (conc.)	Green/reddish brown	+
6.	Tannin	MeOH	5% FeCl ₃ + H ₂ SO ₄ (dil.)	Reddish brown	+
7.	Saponins	H ₂ O	Shaken with 2ml H ₂ O	Frothing	+
8.	α -amino acids	H ₂ O	Ninhydrin reagent	Pink spot	+
9.	Proteins	H ₂ O	Millon's reagent (heated)	White ppt. turned red when heated	+
10.	Reducing sugar	H ₂ O	1 ml H ₂ O and moxyure equal part fehling'A and B	Brick red ppt.	+
11.	Starch	H ₂ O	Iodine solution	Deep blue	+
12.	Carbohydrates	H ₂ O	10 % a-naphthol and conc: H ₂ SO ₄ 1 ml Benedict's reagent and boil for a few minutes	Brick red ppt.	+

Elemental analysis of powdered leaves of *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham.

When the elements present in powdered leaves were quantitatively determine by EDXRF, it was found that calcium (Ca), potassium (K), are found as principal elements and Sulphur (S), Manganese (Mn), Iron (Fe), Strontium (Sr) and Copper (Cu) found to be trace elements.

According to AAS, toxic elements such as Arsenic (As), Lead (Pb), Cadmium (Cd) are found in the leaves of *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham. The results were shown in Tables 2 and 3 and Figures 6 and 7.

Table 2. Elemental analysis of *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham. by using EDXRF

No.	Elements	Percentage present in leaves
1	Cl (Chlorine)	1.371 %
2	K (Potassium)	0.669 %
3	Ca (Calcium)	0.303 %
4	S (Sulphur)	0.236 %
5	Fe (Iron)	0.068 %
6	Mn (Manganese)	0.013 %
7	Bromium (Br)	0.004 %
8	Zinc (Zn)	0.002 %
9	Copper (Cu)	0.001 %

Figure 6. Relative concentration of elements contained in leaves of *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham.**Table 3. Toxic elements analyzed by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS)**

No.	Element	(mg/L)
1	As (Arsenic)	1.509
2	Pb (Lead)	0.523
3	Cd (Cadmium)	0.402

Figure 7. Toxic elements (AAS) contained in leaves of *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham.

Determination of antioxidant activity

Free radical scavenging activity of 95% ethanolic and aqueous extract of leaves of *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham. were measured by using DPPH assay method. Ethanolic extract shows more antioxidant activity than aqueous extract. The results of percent of radical scavenging activity and IC₅₀ (50% Inhibition Concentration) values were shown in table 4 and figures 8 and 9.

Table 4. Antioxidant activity of leaves of *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham.

Concentration	% Radical scavenging activity (% RSA)						IC ₅₀
	25	50	100	200	400	800	
Ethanolic extract	-5.48	0.58	6.63	87.03	97.40	97.40	156.19
Aqueous extract	-3.75	-2.88	-2.88	-2.02	20.46	20.46	671.06

Figure 8. Radical scavenging activity (RSA %)

Figure 9. IC₅₀ values

Discussion and Conclusion

In phytochemical analysis, the preliminary phytochemical screening carried out on the leaves of *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham. The result showed that alkaloids, glycosides, phenolic compounds flavonoids, steroids/terpenoids, tannins, saponins, α -Amino acids, proteins, reducing sugar, starch and carbohydrates were observed. These metabolites have been shown to be responsible for the therapeutic activity of plants (Trease and Evans, 2002). The presence of bioactive secondary metabolites derived from the leaves of *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham. are used in medicinal purposes for human beings. So, *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham may be used as medicinal plant.

The elemental analysis of Energy Dispersive X-ray Fluorescence Spectroscopy (EDXRF) revealed that Chlorine (Cl), Potassium (K), Calcium (Ca), Sulphur (S) are found as principal constituents. Iron (Fe), Manganese (Mn), Bromine (Br), Zinc (Zn), Copper (Cu), Strontium (Sr), Rubidium (Rb) are found to be trace elements. Chlorine is the highest concentration among other elements. Chlorine is essential for life. It is mostly present in cell fluid as a negative ion to balance the positive (mainly sodium) ions. It is also present in extracellular fluid (eg. blood) to balance to the positive (mainly sodium) ions. (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chlorine>). The result indicated that *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham. may be used as medicinal plant because essential elements Ca, S, K, Cl, Fe, Zn, Cu and Mn were present in the leaves.

According to Atomic Absorption Spectrometer, arsenic, lead and mercury are trace constituents in the leaves of *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham. The concentration of arsenic were higher than other metals. The poisonous level of organic As for human is 60 mg/L (<http://www.tuberose.com>). Thus, As contained in leaves were not harmful on human health.

Therefore, the selected plant, *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham. may be useful for the preparation of medicine.

Currently, antioxidants are believed to help protect the body from free radical damage. The DPPH radical was widely used in the model system to investigate the radical scavenging activities of several natural compounds or crude mixture such as ethanol extract of plants. Antioxidant activity of leaves of *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham was also investigated in this research. The result showed that IC₅₀ values of ethanolic extract are less than aqueous extract. Since, the lower IC₅₀ values, the higher free radical scavenging activity. Therefore, antioxidant activity of ethanolic extract was more effective than the aqueous extract.

In conclusion, the selected plant possesses therapeutic phytochemical constituents, essential elements which is required for human body, and has a property of antioxidant activity. Local people used this plant by eating fruits as a vegetable. So, *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham. is saved to be used as both medicinal plant and nutritious vegetable. Therefore, the *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham possesses many medicinal values and it can be used as medicine not only for folkloric use but also widely use for traditional medicine. So other bioactive compounds should be isolated from the various plant parts of *Sonneratia apetala* Buch.-Ham.

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